

Adaption of Criminology Students to Foreign Cultures

A Research Paper Presented to the Faculty of the Criminal Justice Education

In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirement For the Course Criminological Research II and Statistics

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It's not the load that breaks you down, it's the way you carry it. – Lou Holtz

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DEDICATION

To the Almighty Father, who guides us all the way and continues to bless us with so much love and care. For our families, who inspire us to do good and support us in every way throughout the study.

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A.A

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M.J.L

J.R.O

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J.A.S

M.T.T

ABSTRACT

In view of the rapidly increasing influences of foreign cultures, some Criminology Students adapt the said foreign cultures. The purpose of this study is to inculcate in the minds to those students the essence of being patriotic. This research will improve the value and quality of the adaption of foreign cultures and the importance of patronizing Filipino Cultures. This study made use of quantitative research methods through a descriptive research design. Three Hundred Thirty-three (333) Third year and Fourth-year Criminology Students who finished the subject Character Formation 1 and 2 of Data Center College of the Philippines were taken as respondents.

It is imperative to know the foreign cultures that DCCP criminology students usually adapt, the various factors that influence them in adapting to such cultures, their level of enjoyment in terms of adapting foreign cultures, and the action plan that can be formulated to strengthen the patriotism and nationalism of the Criminology Students

Based on the findings, it was therefore recommended that in order to in still in Criminology Students the essence of patriotism, there should be specific programs to enhance patriotism and nationalism. This study will serve as an eye-opener and a baseline for criminology students to assess whether they are really putting into practice what they are learning.

Keywords:- Adaption, Filipino Culture, Patriotism, Nationalism, Criminology Students, Foreign Culture.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TITLE PAGE	Page No.
Approval Sheet	2143
Acknowledgement	2144
Dedication	2145
Abstract	2146
Table of Contents	2147
List of Figures	2148
List of Tables	2148
CHAPTER ONE THE PROBLEM AND ITS SETTING	2149
A. Introduction	2149
B. Background of the Study	2149
C. Statement of the Problem	2150
D. Theoretical Framework	2150
E. Scope and Delimitation	2152
F. Significance of the Study	2152
G. Definition of Terms	2152
CHAPTER TWO REVIEW AND RELATED LITERATURE	2153
A. Culture	2153
B. The Importance of Culture	2154
C. Characteristics of Culture	2154
D. Philippine Culture	2154
E. Understanding the Filipino Culture	2155
F. Patriotism in the Philippines	2155
G. Threats to Filipino Patriotism	2156
H. The Essence of Foreign Culture	2156
I. Different Cultural Traditions Around the World	2156
J. Filipino and Filipino American Culture	2157
K. Patriotism in the Nation Building	2157
L. Patriotism in Malaysia	2158
CHAPTER THREE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	2159
A. Research Method	2159
B. Population and Locale of the Study	2159
C. Research Instrument	2159
D. Data Gathering Procedure	2159
E. Treatment of Data	2159
CHAPTER FOUR PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA	2161
A. Foreign Cultures that are usually adapted by Criminology Students	2161
B. Factors that influence the respondents in adapting foreign cultures	2162
C. Participants level of enjoyment in adapting foreign cultures	2163
CHAPTER FIVE SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	2164
A. Summary of the Findings	2164
B. Conclusion	2164
C. Recommendations	2164
D. Proposed Strategic Plan	2165
REFERENCES	2166
APPENDICES	2168
Appendix "A" Letter to the Registrar	2168
Appendix "B" Letter to Conduct the Study	2169
Appendix "C" Letter to the Respondents	2170
Appendix "D" Survey Questionnaire	2171
Appendix "E" Documentation of Distribution of Survey Questionnaire	2173

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure No.	Title	Page No.
1	The Research Paradigm	2151

LIST OF TABLES

Table No.	Title	Page No.
1	Foreign Cultures that are adapted by Criminology students	2161
2	Factors influence the respondents in adapting foreign culture	2161
3	Participants' Level of Enjoyment in Adapting Foreign Cultures	2162
4	Strategic Plan in Strengthening the Patriotism and Nationalism of Criminology Students (Matrix)	2165

CHAPTER ONE

THE PROBLEM AND ITS SETTING

A. Introduction

Culture can be defined as a part of the environment made by humans. It is the set of meanings that a group in a time and place come to adapt or develop, and these meanings facilitate smooth social coordination, clarify group boundaries, and provide a space for innovation (Parker,2016). Patriotism is a sentiment of love and dedication to one's nation. Patriotism does not exist by itself in human existence; it must be nourished, fertilized, and fostered in order to be powerful in the soul. (Sulaiman,2018).

The influence of media in the 21st century has had both beneficial and harmful consequences. One of the latter is the fact that the youth are easily influenced by the things they see online, from clothes to values. While it is true that breaking the norm is not a bad thing to do, doing such excessively may lead to disorder, both socially and personally. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the youth, especially students, have been exposed to various foreign cultures, as a result of their extensive media consumption. Although not all, this has prompted some of them to favor foreign cultures more than their own. Sadly, this could be one of the most compelling reasons why the youth may lose their patriotism or love for their country. Repeatedly the conduct of this study is of utmost importance because as the national hero of the Philippines, Dr. Jose Rizal, once said, “*Ang kabataan ang pag-asa ng bayan*” (“the youth are the hope of the nation”).

According to McGuire (2017), a country's culture influences the way its citizens think and behave with respect to risks, opportunities, and rewards. The author proposes a process whereby a culture's response to risk, opportunities, and rewards influences entrepreneurial activity and economic creativity (innovation), and national innovation influences national prosperity. According to the author, a proclivity to foster innovation, and make capital and resources available, is a reflection of shared cultural values.” National prosperity can be viewed as a by-product of innovation. Rising living standards are found in countries where enterprises grow more productive by generating more complex sources of competitive advantage based on knowledge, investment, insight, and innovation. Innovative solutions have an effect on a company's revenues and, as a result, on the wealth of nations.

With comparison to the Philippines and Indonesia, globalization or simply the introduction of foreign goods and cultures, has a favorable influence on the Philippines' economic situation (Guinigundo, 2018). While in Indonesia, it has both good and bad consequences. In terms of language monitoring, the introduction of foreign culture has had an impact on the Filipino language since Filipinos have grown more sensitive and cautious in their use of their native tongue (Conti & Hayas, 2019). According to Tabuena (2022), Filipino artists have already adapted more to the culture and arts of other nations than to their own cultural origins, as a result of variables such as the entry of foreign cultures, current technology adaptation, and many more. These may seem to be of little significance when discussing patriotism, but they are sufficient evidence that Filipinos are already adapting more to the culture and influences of other nations rather than their own.

In connection with this study, it has long been a common knowledge how criminology students are viewed as individuals who are loyal to their own countries, and as mentioned by Estipona (2020), studying criminology is to uphold justice and righteousness by crime prevention, crime investigation and detection, and to catch the criminals and bring them justice. Being motivated by righteousness, as well as having a sense of justice is a must to fulfill law enforcement duties and these values are created through character development by parental guidance and example, understanding what is right and not, having an innate desire to serve, generosity, compassion, and love of God, family, community, and country.

B. Background of the Study

In view of the rapidly increasing influences of foreign cultures, some Criminology students adapt foreign cultures. The purpose of this research study is to inculcate in the minds of those students the essence of patriotism. Also, this study will serve as an eyeopener and a baseline for Criminology students to assess whether they are really putting into practice what they are learning.

One of the many problems in adapting foreign cultures with some Criminology students is that, they prefer the foreign ways. Filipinos tend to forget their own products, cultures, and way of living and they choose to follow foreign ways. They support imported products rather than Philippine-made products. They admire foreign music, celebrities, and fashion over local ones. They fancy watching Hollywood movies rather than Filipino movies. There is evidence that nationhood and the domestic strength of the nation-state are being substantially weakened as a result of globalization and economic integration. Nationalism, in a sense, has lost its role as the centrifugal force of Philippine history, because markets and commodities now dictate the consequences of national decisions. The Philippines is growing increasingly exocentric. They place a high value on non-Filipino items such as Filipino music, arts, language, fashion, and even the media. The modern-day Filipinos' clothing style and fashion sense have been influenced by their native lineage, Spanish colonizers, and Americans, as indicated by the sequence of events in Philippine history. In addition to the aforementioned considerations, Filipinos now adapt their manner of dressing as a consequence of the impact of what is displayed by the media on television, fashion shows, and so on. Aside from colonial and media influences, the

climate in the Philippines has affected Filipino clothing design. With a tropical climate (dry and rainy seasons), early Filipinos wore colorful woven clothes, typically with complex beadwork and other *ornam* a sort of a collarless shirt, which eventually became embellished with laces, trimmings, buttons, and a collar, where the Barong Tagalog evolved. The *Bahag*, on the other hand, was a form of loincloth or G-string. For climatic reasons, modern Filipinos choose to wear T-shirts with *maong* (jeans) trousers for men and skirts for women. The Americans introduced the "jeans and T-shirts" look to the Filipinos.

This study aimed to know the foreign culture that the Criminology students usually adapted, and to determine what level of enjoyment students have with the foreign culture that influences their adaption and the factors that influenced them to adapt to foreign culture. In this study, the researchers were able to determine the differences between Filipino culture and the foreign culture, such as the quality of their movies, foods, products, and their tradition.

C. Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to determine the adaption of Criminology Students to Foreign Culture.

Specifically, it sought and answers to the following:

- What are the foreign cultures that DCCP criminology students usually adapt?
- What are the factors that influence DCCP criminology students in adapting foreign cultures?;
- What is the level of enjoyment of DCCP criminology students in term of adapting foreign cultures? and
- What action plan can be formulated to strengthen the patriotism and nationalism of the Criminology Students?

D. Theoretical Framework

The following are the theories that are related to foreign culture consumption on patriotism:

➤ Cultural Proximity Theory

According to Straubhaar (1991), cultural proximity is the tendency to select media products from one's own culture. The rise of regional media production is coherent with concept of cultural proximity. For media to best resonate with the cultural disposition of viewers, the subject matter and the ogler must be in line with the same cultural linguistic or geo-linguistic.

Asian inclination for Korean programs shows that they convey consideration for Asian cultural frames, which include high morality, love, and sacrifice. The study's analysis exhibited that Korean programs satisfy Asian emotional needs by being easy to adapt to a similar lifestyle, cultural proximity, and gravity. Although the language is the main factor that audiences connect with, viewers go further than language to include history, religion, ethnicity and culture in numerous senses. (Alanzalon,2011).

This theory is relevant to this study because it focuses on the intuitively attractive idea that individuals prefer their own produced media products over others. This has evolved as a key theoretical concept for describing audience behavior in a world where varied people have increasing access to increasingly plentiful media settings and Criminology Students are becoming more and more interested in engaging with media from other cultures on a variety of levels. The influence of the actors who appeared in certain dramas, such as K-dramas and other foreign television, criminology students are drawn to Korean dramas than the Filipino dramas, they want to learn the language as well as about their literature, film, history, politics and popular culture.

➤ Social Identity Theory

According to Tajfel and Turner (1986), Social Identity Theory defined a group as a collection of people who categorized themselves as belonging to the same social category and internalize the category's social identity-defining attributes to define and evaluate themselves-attributes that capture and accentuate intragroup similarities and inter-group differences. According to Tajfel and Turner (1979), social identity refers to the ways that people's self-concepts are based on their membership in social groups. It addresses the ways that social identities affect people's attitudes and behaviors regarding them in group and outgroup. Social identity is the most influential when individuals consider membership in a particular group to be central to their self-concept, and they feel strong emotional ties to the group.

This theory is relevant to the study since it suggests that individuals experience collective identity based on their membership in a group, such as racial/ethnic and gender identities that affect them to act accordingly. This theory also explains that individual suits themselves to others to feel a sense of belongingness.

➤ *Consumer Oppression Theory*

According to Arnold and Thompson (2005), Consumer Oppression Theory believes that purchaser culture leads to the closure of conventional cultures and values and forces a common culture to orbit around products and goods. The belief is that the consumer actually has very little influence and is constrained into consumer culture through peer pressure and media hype. The idea that someone wants a bigger television because it is what everyone else is doing, is an example. Sociologists would debate that many of the choices consumers make are not actually founded on individualistic wants, but instead, based on what group and consumer culture say they need.

➤ *Critical Theory*

According to Horkheimer (1985), Critical Theory is an attempt to examine and critique society as a whole by identifying the underlying assumptions in social life that impede people from participating in a real democracy (Kellner, 1989). Critical Theory offers systematic and complete theories of modernity's trajectory and diagnoses of some of its shortcomings, pathologies, and destructive repercussions. According to Kellner, Critical Theory has traditionally been committed to the idea of modernity and progress while recognizing how elements of today's society can cause issues for individuals and society. In certain aspects, Weber's critique of modern society's rationalization might be considered a critical theory.

Relevant to this study, it also suggests that people change their perceptions because of the involvement of social media. Because of the introduction of many cultures or products in social media, people got interested and become curious about that culture and thereafter start loving it.

Fig 1 The Research Paradigm

This study adapts the Input-Process-Output (IPO) Model which has historically been the prevalent method to understanding and explaining team operation and continues to utilize a strong effect on group research today. The structure is based on classic systems theory, which states that the general structure of a system is as important in deciding how effective it will function as its individual components. More prominently, the IPO model has a causal organization, wherein, the outputs are a function of various group processes, which are in turn, persuaded by numerous input variable quantity. (Hackman, 1987).

In this study, there were three (3) input variables which are: (1) the foreign cultures usually adapted by criminology students, (2) the factors that influence them, and (3) the level of their enjoyment in adapting such cultures. In the process, an analysis of the adaption of Criminology students to foreign cultures through a survey questionnaire and treatment of data through weighted mean. As to the output, the researchers created an Action Plan to strengthen the essence of patriotism and nationalism to Criminology Students.

E. Scope and Delimitation

This study covers the adaption of Criminology students to foreign cultures. The participants were limited to third year and fourth year Criminology students who finished the subject Character Formation 1 and 2, from the Second Semester of S.Y 2021-2022 to the First Semester of S.Y 2022-2023.

F. Significance of the Study

The research was conducted with the purpose of giving critical information and knowledge about the chosen topic from respondents, recent studies of the thesis, and associated sites that are required for the expected importance to individuals, as follow:

➤ *Adults.*

Through the findings of this study, it would guide adults to strengthen their patriotic behavior and minimize foreign consumption among their relatives. This could be used as a tool to help Filipinos become more patriotic.

➤ *Criminology Instructors.*

The outcome of the study will guide Criminology instructors in developing efficient strategies for restoring the Criminology Students' patriotic behavior. Moreover, the result may help them understand the needs of students and their weaknesses, and could serve as a tool for determining the level of foreign consumption of Criminology students.

➤ *Criminology Students.*

This study will give them an awareness of how they consume foreign cultures, and may affect their patriotic behavior and how they can overcome these through the responses of the respondents which will serve as a guide for them to know the importance of being a patriotic person.

➤ *Future Researchers.*

The result of this study would serve as baseline information for students who would be conducting studies about foreign culture consumption on the patriotism of Criminology students.

➤ *Researchers.*

Conducting the study serve as an authentic learning experience that will help the researchers sharpen their skills and acquire new knowledge.

G. Definitions of Terms

For clarification, these terms were used in this study, and were defined as follows:

➤ *Adaption-*

It is the copying of someone's behavior, beliefs and style that fulfil their needs in life.

➤ *Culture –*

It is deemed as shared meanings and behaviors that people adapt over time; as well as learned and shared thought and behavior patterns that are specific to that population.

➤ *Filipino Culture –*

It is the blend of traditions and beliefs that symbolize Filipino behavior that Filipinos are family oriented and often religious with an appreciation for art, fashion, music and foods.

➤ *Patriotism –*

Loving of one's country by adapting and consuming their own traditions, beliefs, and style.

➤ *Peers –*

It is a group of people or companies that share similar characteristics with one another, they are the ones who encourage different types of styles that may patronize one another.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This chapter presents an extensive review of literature and studies that have relevance to the investigation of the problem under the study. It provides the basis for conducting the present study and differences with the previous research conducted relevant to the subject.

A. Culture

A factor of the setting created by humans is what is meant by culture. It is the compilation of meanings that a group in an actual time and place comes to adapt or establish, and these meanings make it easier for people to perform together socially, make group boundaries clear, and leave chance for creativeness (Parker,2016). A feeling of love and devotion for one's country is called patriotism. In order to become strong in the soul, patriotism needs to be nurtured, cultivate, and promoted in human existence. (Sulaiman, 2018). The culture of a nation affects how its people perceive and respond to risk, opportunity, and rewards. Therefore, the author suggests a process whereby national innovation influences national prosperity, and entrepreneurial activity and economic creativity (innovation) are influenced by a culture's response to risk, opportunity, and rewards (McGuire,2017). It is believed that a tendency to support innovation and make finance and resources available reflects shared cultural ideals, says the author. National prosperity can be viewed as a by-product of innovation. Rising living standards are found in countries where enterprises grow more productive by generating more complex sources of competitive advantage based on knowledge investment, insight, and innovation. Innovative solutions have an effect on a company's revenues and, as a result, on the wealth of nations.

The American culture is one of the most culturally varied nations in the world (London Economics, 2021). Almost every expanse of the world has shaped American culture, most notably the English who populated the country commencing in the early 1600s. Indigenous Americans, Latin Americans, Africans, and Asians, have all had an impact on American culture. The United States is sometimes labelled as a "melting pot" in which distinctive cultures have influenced their own distinct "flavours" to American civilisation. Just as cultures from all over the world have induced American culture, American culture now impacts the balance of the world.

Meanwhile, Europe is a continent that is a rich and diverse mosaic of cultural and creative expressions, an inheritance from previous generations of Europeans, and a legacy for those to come. It comprises natural, constructed, and archaeological structures, museums, monuments, artworks, historic towns, literary, musical, and audio-visual works, as well as European individuals' knowledge, practices, and traditions (European Commission, 2018).

On the other hand, Korean Culture is a vibrant cultural heritage, which includes music, art, literature, dance, architecture, dress, and food which provides a beautiful blend of history and contemporary. At present, Korean arts and culture are attracting many enthusiasts around the world. Many of Korea's young talents are now competing in the world's most famous music and dance competitions, and their literary masterpieces are being translated into many other languages for worldwide readers. Korean Dansaekhwa (monochrome paintings) have recently been the topic of the art world. Today as the world constantly improves, Korean culture progressively influences the people in the world, especially Filipinos, and has flourished in the years since it first hit the country.

Korean foods and stuff are obvious in our marketplace today. We can perceive that the increase of Korean stores in malls, commercial centres, and other involvements of the country has proved K-stores and restaurants with K-beauty goods, K-clothes, and K-food products. The people marvel at beauty since they are astonished by how Koreans dress up, their style, the food they eat, and how they present themselves in the world we live in today. There are stuff most cannot give explanation about how people get influenced by Korean culture, but we can see that Korean dramas and music were able to edify us to think and act differently. The melody of the music, features of their K-pop idols, K-pop group presentation style, and they are hard to memorize and unique killer dance moves made their fans like and idolize them, despite the lyrics, of which they do not comprehend. Because of K-pop, there are fans that are now head over heels for them. Filipino youths are also influenced by Korean looks, to have a Korean look is to have a Korean hairstyle in order to have that Korean sense of fashion. Korean hairstyles became the trend in the Philippines today. (Kapuso Mo Jessica Soho, 2010).

In addition, Indian culture has had a major impact or effect on many other empires. Religions are also heavily inspired by Indians. The only country in the whole world that has many religions in India. In India, there are several religious convictions such as Hinduism, Jainism, Islam, Sikhism, Buddhism, and Christianity exist. Performing arts was a key thing in Indian literature. In those days only very cool and fine arts were made which astonished the majority of other country people and made interest in it. Music in those days was enjoyable and gives a fresh feeling to the mind, heart, and body. Dramas also play a vital role in India's style of life. People used to explore the Mahabharata and used to play those in theatres and also with the only imaginative way they used to think. (Reddy, 2017)

And lastly, Japanese Culture is sometimes portrayed as homogeneous, despite the fact that there are various parts of Japanese culture and society that are varied. Many people take pride in their origin and the geographical variances that happen throughout Japan. Nonetheless, mutual themes found throughout Japanese culture include a sagacity of identity-based on social groups and residence of birth, a polite and humble communiqué style, a pragmatic approach to situations and challenges, and a gratitude for and enjoyment of artistic activities and forms of entertainment. Japan's cultural values are thoroughly rooted in all expressions of life, and will always impact family, work, and social interactions. In Japan, family ties are sharp, uniting not just present extended family delegates but also generations of lineage. You will notice that Japanese people do not express themselves physically in public, and you will not see any kissing or hugging on the streets. Hands are shown being held by friends, parents, and children. (Kanagy,2020).

B. *The Importance of Culture*

Culture facilitates things for two important reasons. For starters, cultures help to provide meaning to events, objects, and people, making the world less strange and terrifying for students. Second, culture clarifies life by allowing students to understand who they are and where they come from. Cultural awareness is very crucial for students, and when combined with strong communication it serves as a key component of academic and social success. The culture in which people grow up shapes their values, goals, and habits, as does knowing other cultures (Meyer,2006).

Culture reflects the values of a group or nation. As a result, culture plays an important role in determining how a community reacts, responds, and develops. Everyone's life in society is influenced by culture. Culture gives you a sense of belonging, especially when everyone speaks the same language. Language evolves in tandem with culture as a result of how individuals in society communicate. A healthy, thriving culture positively reflects a diverse community. Culture is critical to a society's development and economic prosperity (Painter, 2020).

C. *Characteristics of Culture*

According to Samovar (2010), people do not usually discuss their culture as the latter takes place below the conscious level, and consequently, people do not understand the influence of a culture that is reflected in and their habits behaviors.

➤ *Culture is Learned.*

People seek meanings to help them understand and make sense of the world from the beginning of their existence; this includes how they perceive and handle certain situations, as well as how they characterize other people who encounter them. Others provide them with this vital knowledge; they learn those cultural characteristics through interactions, observation, and imitation (Samovar, 2010).

➤ *Culture is Shared.*

According to Haviland (2005), culture is the primary component that determines which behaviors are appropriate in which circumstances; people share a cultural identity, which is why they can predict and comprehend individuals from their own culture. Culture, as a shared set of ideas, values, perceptions, and behavioral norms, is the common component that explains people's actions to other members of their community. It enables them to predict how other members will behave in a given situation and teaches them how to respond appropriately.

➤ *Culture is Passed Down from Generation to Generation.*

For any culture to survive, its members must pass it on to the next generation; the values, concepts, and attitudes that are vital components of that culture must be learned by the following generation (Porter, 2010).

➤ *Culture is Dynamic.*

Culture is continually evolving due to factors such as migration, technology, and globalization. Cultures are now more exposed to one another than they have ever been before as a result of globalization. However, it is important to remember that these changes only occur on the surface of civilizations, leaving the underlying structure of culture, which includes essential values, morals, ethics, and so on, as well as religious activities which remain unaffected (McDonald,2010)

D. *Philippine Culture*

Filipinos are educated in both English and Tagalog, making the country one of the most English-speaking in the world. Unlike other Asian countries, the Philippines has been prompted by a diversity of other republics and philosophies as a result of Spanish and American colonization, Japanese occupation during WWII, and trade with China, the Pacific Islands, Portugal, and Australia (Nadal, 2011).

Filipino culture is a radiant story that recounts the nation's changes over time. People's practices represent their beliefs, solidarity with others, bond with nature, and commemoration of life. The Filipinos' allure is found in their smiles, in the numerous religious festivals that honour the environment, the Divine, and the sequences of life, and in the asset of *pakikipag-kapwa-tao*, which merits relationships with both groups and guests. The concept of *kapwa* (others) is deeply rooted in the Filipino spirit.

The Philippines has a philosophy in which the East meets the West. The Filipinos have a definite Asian legacy as well as a strong Western practice. Chinese traders, Spanish conquistadors, and American leaders all had an impact on modern Filipino citizens.

Filipinos are well-known for their pleasantness, particularly toward intercontinental travelers. Because of their thorough ties to Spanish culture, Filipinos are emotional and passionate about life in a way that exists more Latin than Asian.

According to Espineda (2013), The Philippines' culture is a combination of traditional Filipino and Spanish Catholic practices, as well as influences from America and other fragments of Asia. Filipinos are typically religious people who admire art, fashion, music, and food. Filipinos are also welcoming people who enjoy having pleasure. This frequently includes get-togethers to sing, dance, and eat. The annual calendar is jam-packed with celebrations, many of which blend pre-Christian costumes and rituals with progressive Catholic beliefs and ideology.

E. Understanding the Filipino Culture

Understanding the complexity of Filipino culture might take time for someone who has never met, seen, or interacted with a Filipino or has never visited the Philippines. Understanding its mysteries is like going into the forest without a decent map and getting lost. Understanding and appreciating Filipino culture and mindset is very rewarding both for one's business and for him/her personally.

The Filipino bloodline, Chinese, Malay, and Spanish are just a limited of the lines that run in the veins of every Filipino. Furthermore, the Americans have had a massive impact, as the Philippines was an American settlement for 50 years. This distinguishing mix of cultures has developed distinct Filipino attributes. Filipinos are outward people that like festivals and are fascinated with singing and dancing. Filipino culture is predominantly family oriented, resulting in laid-back approaches. Although they may not have the definite richness that many Western countries do, they are prosperous in many respects because of their deeply related social and familial connections. When it comes to religion, the Philippines is Asia's biggest Christian nation, and people take their faith critically. Most Filipinos attend a weekly provision, with the church serving as the pillar of every local community. It is quite usual for people to join the same church as all of their family and friends, and it is critical to be sensible of the loyalty that this creates when dealing with Filipino personnel. Ethnicity in the Philippines is compiled of more than 80 tribes each with its own local language. English is instructed in all schools and is the leading mode of transmission for individuals of many dialects. Despite being divided by islands, Filipinos have sturdy cultural ties and a strong family and community support scheme. Filipinos are always compassionate to their less fortunate *kababayan* (countrymen). Everyone, regardless of class, is expected to act with humility, civility, and respect at all times. It is usual for Filipinos to refer their superiors or elders, which is a distinctive feature of the Filipino culture as "Sir" or "Ma'am". Additionally, people can occasionally perceive them use the expression "*ho*" or "*po*" when they talk as this is a way of demonstrating respect.

Lone family and kinship, Filipinos are collective and love to distribute what they have specifically with food. This is why it is normal to see family meals at most restaurants, which are just as likely to be divided by co-workers. Surprisingly, if one dines among Filipinos, he/she will learn that no one likes to finish the final bite on the plate. Filipinos have a fairly regulated way of life and are not as forceful or independent as Europeans. This is in part because of the extensive impact of family. Filipino children, no matter how old, are likely to be significantly inclined, led, and steered by their parents. Another popular Filipino practice is "*utang na loob*," or obligation of gratitude. If one does anything kind for a Filipino, they will typically give in return. It is crucial to consider this while dealing with Filipino employees. Because if they are handled and rewarded properly, they will most likely remain with you for a long time. Filipinos normally do not leave home until they are ready to tie the knot, and even then, it is sometimes upsetting for the parents. Filipinos often believe they owe their parentage a great deal for raising them and leaving them in nursing homes is unheard of. It is common for children to look after their parents as they get aged.

F. Patriotism in the Philippines

Luis Rodriguez Varela, a Filipino Creole, was one of the first men who exhibited Philippine Nationalism and Patriotism. However, at his time, the term Filipino refer to Spaniards born in the Philippines and not the native people. Varela researched in France during the Age of Enlightenment and employed what he discovered to Philippine trials.

In his book, "Historic Proclamation", he called for equal rights for both the Spaniards and the native people, which gradually made the term Filipino pertinent to anyone born in the Philippines (Roces, 2010).

However, Varela's work did not go to waste because his works motivated others. Creole and Padre Palaez advocated the rights of Filipino priests and led the group for the secularization of the Philippine parishes. His life was cut short by an earthquake, but his activism was carried on by one of his followers, Jose Burgos. Burgos, along with Mariano Gomez and Jacinto Zamora, was killed in the famous Cavite mutiny. From then on, history perceived one of the incidents that ignited the nationalistic spirit in the young mind of Dr. Jose P. Rizal, the Philippines' National Hero (Delos Santos, n.d.). "El Filibusterismo," one of Rizal's works, was devoted to Gomburza's memory. Rizal gave a new voice to the agony of Filipinos in his debut novel, "Noli Me Tangere," which became one of the channels of the Philippine revolution (Roces, 2010).

Aside from Rizal, numerous individualities such as Andres Bonifacio, Gregorio del Pilar, Emilio Aguinaldo, and the like were also roused by the deleterious claws of the Spaniards and started to combat for the Philippines. The stream of Philippine history was altered by their works and ambitions. Their patriotic feelings and nationalistic objectives were the push for the 1896 Philippine Revolution's victory (Delos Santos, n.d.).

G. Threats to Filipino Patriotism

The causation of state interaction may be recognized and based principally on the significant and predominant expansion of globalization processes. These processes qualify individuals to classify themselves as citizens of a specific country, and as well as granting numerous opportunities and prospective socio-political attributes. In modern times, when an individual confronts social encounters such as self-identity formation, cultural diffusion, and patriotic awareness, it becomes increasingly noteworthy and vital, which these matters allow to encourage and incubate the essential values of the nation and ensure its safeguarding. Furthermore, additional alarming problem brought by globalization is the captivation with the West, its culture, norms, lifestyle, fashion, music, technology and etc. Because of admiration for the Western's expertise in cultural and technical elements, some of its famed and sensational representations are imitated. It can cause an individual to dislike and disdain their own culture and character as an individual citizen of his/her country, as well as setting away the national heritage, history, and customs. Some of the cultural differences conveyed in behavioural appearances, and the way of observation often become the source of humiliation rather than pride. The most distinguished menace to patriotic values is the following: national nihilism and cosmopolitanism. First, national nihilism relate to the constant pursuit and fabrication of vast quantities of things, which leads to repulsion and disrespect for any national principles, as well as apathy in the connection to the home country. It is the juncture at which an individual refuses history, culture, and customs while also isolating himself/herself from the nation. Alternatively, cosmopolitanism can be the result and effect embedded in nihilism. It gives an individual to classify him/herself as a citizen of the world and sort that he or she belongs to a certain human race. It is clearly apparent in their action of their own people as well as individuals from other nations, both of which are directly manipulated as a tool and instruments for realizing personal aspirations and gains.

Modern identity crisis does not just affect millennials, but it may also influence the entire society from a broader perspective or scale. The reason for this is that state affairs are dynamic and change from time to time in different circumstances. The diversity of these changes encompasses a large portion of our everyday life, which can clearly lead to severe challenges in adapting to them.

H. The Essence of Foreign Culture

The effect of national culture is felt at several levels, from the individual to the larger community. At this point, it is worth emphasizing that in the literature on the subject organizations are seen as having particular importance in transforming societies toward sustainability (Hopwood, 2005). According to (Ansah, 2019), National cultural values can influence the way people set up and develop organizations. Organizational culture, in turn, has an influence on an organization's performance (Cameron et al., 2006). As a result, they are seen as a strategic factor in light of a resource-based organizational theory (Genç, 2013).

The influence of national culture on organizational culture may be described using institutional theory as follows: companies adapt to society's ideals and as a result gain acceptance and obtain the necessary resources (Chen, 2010). In turn, according to stakeholder theory, an organization's responsibility is to respond to the expectations of its stakeholders as well as a society and its culture can be treated as a stakeholder (Henriksson,2020). In terms of the distinctions between national and organizational culture, it may be stated that national cultural characteristics are founded in values learned before the age of ten; children learn them from parents who also acquired them before age of ten, so they are quite stable and take generations to be changed (Mansaray, 2020). In turn, organizational cultural traits are deeply established in workplace activities and, as a result, may change quicker than national culture.

I. Different Cultural Traditions Around the World

According to TIROSH (2020), culture is the combination of a particular society or people's ideas, beliefs, customs, arts, and social behaviors. It is the core of that civilization something profoundly embedded and unique to that specific community. A tradition is also deeply ingrained. It refers to a particular action, event, or habit that has been passed down from generation to generation. People's many traditions are inextricably linked to their various civilizations. These distinctive cultural behaviors frequently contribute to their sense of self and place. This is true whether they follow the custom in question or not - it is still a part of their cultural history and participating in it (or not) tells something about who they are and whom they aim to be.

In Italy, some traditions span more than one country. Religious traditions are a good illustration of this (though there are, of course, many religious traditions that are unique to a single society or people). From pilgrimages to celebrations on specific days, religious traditions around the world are immensely important to people. They provide a sense of spiritual and personal connection and assist people in defining themselves and their beliefs. Many religious traditions are also linked to food. Catholics, for example, ingest an unleavened bread wafer during holy communion. They believe they are devouring the body of Jesus Christ through a mystical process called as transubstantiation. Furthermore, in India, many cultures around the world have traditions that relate to clothing. The color of a bride's wedding gown is typically customary and regarded to bring good luck. Brides in China wear red, whereas brides in the United States wear white. Hindu brides would also wear red, either as a wedding sari or a lehenga

(this differs according to the region of India that the bride lives in). In the United Kingdom, their cultural tradition are the Magpies, it is not just in the area of bridal clothing where people see traditions linked to luck. Indeed, many traditions are based on superstitions, which are commonly held but irrational beliefs, frequently associated with luck and the supernatural. Magpies are an excellent example of this. Some Native American tribes practiced wearing magpie feathers as a symbol of bravery. Many Christian cultures, however, think that witnessing a lone magpie signals ill luck. Various customs have evolved over time to stave off ill luck. Some people salute, some say good morning to the solitary bird, and yet others simply doff their caps. Such instances of traditions and rituals associated with warding off ill luck and boosting good luck may be found all throughout the world. Red Envelopes is one of the traditions in China plenty of cultures have traditions that relate to holiday periods.

On New Year's customs in China, for example, is the distribution of red envelopes carrying money. As part of the festivities, parents and grandparents frequently give them to their children. it is also a country where incense is very popular with the Filipinos and also with the bracelet which some the student is fond of using it. Lastly, is the Flamenco in Spain, music and dance form an important part of the culture of people across the world. Traditional music and dance differ greatly from culture to culture, both in terms of the instruments utilized and the dancing technique. They do, however, have a power that transcends ethnic barriers.

J. Filipino and Filipino American Culture

Filipino family values carried back from the Philippines have heavily affected Filipino American traditions. These values focus on, and are based on three major Filipino cultural traits: *utang na loob* (debt of gratitude), and *pakikisama* (harmony). The idea of *utang na loob* refers to a reciprocal obligation, which is frequently shown as an act of compassion. (Cimmarusti, 1996). *Pakikisama* is togetherness or harmony where people display equal respect and mindfulness towards family members (Cimmarusti, 1996). The concept of respect is fundamental in Filipino society. Respect is held in great respect, particularly for seniors within the family or the larger society. The term "elder" refers not just to grandparents, but also to cousins or other family members who are older in age. Elders are defined as those who have enough experience and wisdom to influence decision-making, regardless of how much older they are than others (Nadal, 2011). On the other hand, Filipinos are encouraged to spend time with their elders to seek guidance or to watch and emulate their triumphs. Overall, respect is required to be shown to everyone in the Filipino culture in order to foster *pakikisama* (harmony), regardless of the gender, age, or race of an individual or group. Subsequently, in exploring Filipino culture, it is evident that Spain's and the United States colonization of the Philippines had considerable impact. English is currently the Philippines' second national language, and it is taught in public schools in accordance with US grammar and comprehension standards (Mulder 2013).

This newly evolved Filipino culture has influenced the emergence and development of Filipino American culture in the United States. The American impact on Filipino American culture varies based on the level of acculturation and assimilation of each individual or household (Choi,2009). According to Agbayani-Siewert (1997), this process of adapting social patterns of another ethnic group is unique to each individual where numerous factors such as age, generation, historical, and nonhistorical demographics within the U.S. and in the Philippines affect each individual.

K. Patriotism in Nation Building

According to Johnson (1989), patriotism has a crucial part and important structure to play in uniting and arranging large-scale societies communally. He also stated that patriotism enables integration, which serves as a basis for concord. Additionally, it leads to self-sacrifices for the common good of the group which is considered the most valuable value. Patriotic ideals have always acted an important task and role in the lives of individuals within the convergence.

The idea that ideas and thoughts satisfy the distinct needs and constraints of different people is not new. In the past years, a lot of findings have been announced and proposed by many social psychologists and sociologists regarding the purpose of beliefs and attitudes. Aside from the essential roles of ideas and attitudes, which is to offer a substantial and profound structure of the world for the individuals, they are also to assist and require in meeting other personal and social conditions. For example, one of the most important purposes of beliefs is to set apart and define the group's borders.

With regard to this, the belief method allows the formation and creation of social identity. Lastly, patriotic beliefs satisfy both the personal demands of the organization's members and the obligations of the group as a social association. In terms of the basic determination of patriotic ideas, one of its personal roles is a sense of belongingness and characteristics. Individuals want a place for themselves because they want to be allied and connected, to be a member of a communal unit, and to develop significant relationships, which patriotic beliefs fulfil. The sense of shared connection is connected to a strong feeling of belonging. Patriotic beliefs not only reinforce a sense of belonging but also added to define the description of a person's social identity. In reality, the sense of fitting and social identity has a link and are tied to one another. Social identity may be established and moulded by a sense of belonging. Abrahams (2018) pointed out that identity, specifically social identity, and group belongings, are indissolubly connected in the sense that one 's conception or definition of who one is (one 's identity) is largely collected of self-descriptions in forms of the defining characteristics of a social group to which one belongs. Recognition with a social group is a psychological state very different from merely being considered as falling into one social classification or another. It is phenomenologically real and has an important self-evaluative result.

L. Patriotism in Malaysia

According to Mohammad (2020), Patriotism and loyalty are not just words that are uttered but come from the heart, the inner spirit of oneself. As a result, the concept of patriotism should be instilled in children early on, since when youngsters love their home, land, and nation, they will grow up appreciating their inheritance, culture, social values, history, heritage, and diversity, and strive to improve Malaysia in any aspect of their lives, either socially, economically or intellectually. Patriotism may be cultivated in Malaysian young via education, awareness, and information. The education system should be tailored to instill not just a sense of pride and dignity, but also a sense of belonging to the country and nation in their hearts and minds. Malaysia is considered to be a one-of-a-kind, multi-racial country with a diverse range of cultures and customs. It works as a melting pot, requiring strong assimilation and nation-building not only to deepen and extend Malaysian adults' and youth's peace and harmony, but also to tear down barriers and bridge gaps in their differences. It takes a strong quality of youth and inspirational individuals with good personalities to bring pride and joy to Malaysia and represent the country locally and globally in the fields of education, commerce, economics, sports, technology, and entertainment. This is vital as only through a deep sense of belonging can Malaysia's younger generation be molded into responsible and mature citizens as well as shaped into charismatic, honest, and respectful future leaders of the country.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the methods of research employed by the researchers in conducting the study which include the research design, the population of the study, the research instrument and its development establishing its validity and reliability, data gathering procedures, and the appropriate statistical treatment of data. It will be conducted.

A. Research Method

This study utilized the quantitative method, using the descriptive research design. According to Sis International Research (2018), quantitative research is a structured way of collecting and analyzing data obtained from different sources. Quantitative research involves the use of computational, statistical, and mathematical tools to derive results.

Descriptive research design is defined as a research method that depicts the characteristics of the populace that is being explored, where data are gathered from the respondents at one point in time. This design always controls more on what the research subject instead than the why of the research topic (Babbie, 1990).

B. Population and Locale of the Study

The participants of this study were the 333 in Third year and Fourth year Criminology students, who finished the subject Character Formation 1 and 2. This study was conducted at Data Center College of the Philippines, Laoag City. Random sampling is a sampling technique in which each member of a population has an equal chance of being chosen, through the use of an unbiased selection method (Simkus, 2022).

C. Research Instrument

The data needed were gathered through a research-made survey questionnaire. The questionnaire is composed of three parts. The first part determined the foreign cultures the respondents usually adapting. The second part is concerned with the factors that influence them to adapt to the foreign culture. The third part gathered their level of enjoyment in adapting foreign culture. The questionnaire was constructed based on the pre-survey gathered from the Criminology students.

D. Data Gathering Procedure

A letter requesting to conduct the study was prepared. The researchers constructed a questionnaire checklist, and was validated by the research adviser. First, the researchers conducted a pre-survey as a basis of composing survey questionnaire. Second, a letter to the registrar was forwarded to determine the number of Criminology students who finished the subjects Character Formation 1 and 2. Third, after the approval of the research questionnaire, the researchers encoded the validated survey-questionnaire. Letter permission to conduct the study was prepared for the Department Head of DCCP-CCJE before administering the questionnaires to the respondents. Following the approval, the questionnaire checklist was distributed to the students of Data Center College of the Philippines. The researchers explained to the respondents the importance of their response to the study. The researchers clarify some terms to the respondents so that respondents could answer the questionnaire with full knowledge of their responsibility as the subject of the study. Also, the researchers requested the respondents to answer with all honesty. After the respondents answered the questionnaire, the researchers collected and tallied the data interpretation. The researchers asked the research adviser to help them in determining the appropriate statistical tools to be used in interpreting the data. Based on the data, the researchers came up with a conclusion and recommendation for this study.

E. Treatment of Data

The data gathered, collected, and tabulated were subjected to analysis and interpretation through the use of appropriate tools. Descriptive statistics was used in this study. The researchers examined the data to identify the level of their enjoyment, and to determine what influences them. The researchers were deepened their perspective through the findings of the collected data. The research was validated to come up with accurate findings.

Weighted mean was used to analyze and interpret the data to determine the foreign culture they usually patronize, the factors that influence them to adapt to the foreign culture, and the level of enjoyment in patronizing such.

A Likert scale is a type of rating scale that is commonly found on survey forms or questionnaires, and is used to measure how people feel about something. It can be beneficial in a variety of situations (Solman, 2020). The 5-point Likert scale was utilized by the researchers to know the descriptive interpretation of the gathered data from the respondents.

Likert scale consists of the mean rating, descriptive interpretation and verbal interpretation.

Legend

Scale	Range	Descriptive Interpretation	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree	Not Highly Influenced
4	3.51-4.50	Agree	Barely Influenced
3	2.51-3.50	Neutral	Highly influenced
2	1.51-2.50	Disagree	Not Influenced
1	1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Poor influenced

CHAPTER FOUR PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION, AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

This chapter delivers the presentation of statistical data of the collected information from the respondents. The subsequent interpretation and analysis of data are combined in this portion of the study.

Culture makes things easy for two important reasons. First, culture helps to provide meaning to events, objects, and a person, which makes the world a less mysterious and frightening place for students. Secondly, culture makes life less confusing, as students are able to know who they are and where they are from. Table 1 presents the different foreign cultures that are being adapted by Criminology students. Table 2 presents the factors that influence them, either through fashion, peers, or social media. Table 3 shows their level of enjoyment in adapting those foreign cultures.

Table 1 Foreign Cultures that are Usually Adapted by Criminology Students. n=333

Variables	Frequency	Rank
Foreign Cultures		
Korean Cultures	102	1
American Cultures	60	2
Chinese Cultures	54	3
Japanese Cultures	50	4
Vietnam Cultures	30	5
European Cultures	25	6
Indian Cultures	11	7
Others (Spanish)	1	8

A. Foreign Cultures that are Usually Adapted by Criminology Students.

The table shows the foreign cultures that are being adapted by Criminology students.

The results of the study reveals that *Korean Culture* ranked no. 1, with a total of 102 answers, and the cultures they mostly adapt is the K-Drama, K-pop, and their food because these three are popular these days through the use of social media. Korean dramas have greatly influenced the food, fashion, cosmetics, music, and entertainment industries, as well as people’s views and preferences since Korean Dramas are one of most popular in Asia since 2000. As to the influence of K-pop on Filipinos, it is now increasing because of the visual, music, choreography, and artistic content of Korean music and videos. Rank no. 2 is the *American Culture* with a total of 60 answers, in which they mostly adapt their Hollywood movies and songs. Rank 3 is *Chinese Culture* with 54 total answers, in which the respondents adapt their *incense and bracelets*. Rank 4 is the *Japanese Culture* with a total of 50 answers. Most of the respondents adapt their culture by watching anime, reading manga, and cuisine culture. Rank 5 is *Vietnam Culture* which has a total of 30 responses. The students adapt their sense of fashion and music. Rank 6 is the *European Culture* with a total of 25 answers. Their fashion and foods are mostly adapted by the respondents. Rank 7 is *Indian Culture* which has a total of 11 answers. Street food is the culture that the respondents adapted. Last rank is the *Spanish Culture* with only 1 answer, in which the respondent adapts their religion.

Table 2 Factors that Influence the Respondents in Adapting Foreign Cultures n=333

Factors	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Fashion		
Buy new fashionable clothes only when they are well-accepted.	3.26	Neutral
Got interested in buying items used by celebrities.	2.65	Neutral
Copy the hairstyle of celebrities.	2.50	Neutral
Purchase clothes based on quality and design.	3.62	Agree
Prefer to buy branded clothes rather than local ones.	2.85	Neutral
Buy clothes endorsed by favorite celebrities.	2.61	Neutral
Risky to buy unbranded products because of their low quality.	2.75	Neutral
Peers		
Got interested in what I saw or heard from my friends.	3.28	Neutral
Choose the same fashion style from my friends.	2.55	Neutral
Listen to the music or watch the same TV shows with friends.	3.13	Neutral
Suit self just to be accepted by friends.	2.53	Neutral
Social Media		
Learned other foods and clothing styles through Facebook and other online platforms	3.71	Agree

Rely more on online deliveries like Shopee, Lazada, food panda, etc.	3.34	Neutral
Got influenced by the online advertising products.	3.05	Neutral
Got influenced by the lifestyle of online Influencer.	2.74	Neutral
Prefer to always shop using social media such as online selling.	3.00	Neutral

B. Factors that Influence the Respondents in Adapting Foreign Cultures

The table shows the result on the factors that influence the participants in adapting foreign cultures as to fashion, peers, and social media.

As to fashion, the result of the study shows the highest weighted mean of 3.62 which is the “purchase of clothes based on quality and design”, next is “buy new fashionable clothes only when they are well-accepted” with a weighted mean of 3.26, the respondents “prefer to by branded clothes than the local ones” with the weighted mean of 2.85, next is “risky to buy unbranded products because of their low quality” with a weighed mean of 2.75, the respondents “got interested in buying items used by celebrities” (2.65), “buying clothes endorsed by favorite celebrities” (2.61), lastly, is “copy the hairstyle of celebrities”, with the lowest weighted mean of 2.50.

Fashion has frequently proven to be a means of self-expression and an important part of cultural identity. According to Brannon and Divita (2015), fashion is a currently popular style or a set of trends that have been accepted by a large audience. Certain fabrics, designs, and accessories for fashion have become essential to forming cultural identities and maintaining cultural traditions. Taking inspiration from the designs and intricacy of other cultures has become the norm in today's fashion industry. Fashion has long been used as a way of expression and the development of cultural identity.

According to Thompson and Haytko (1997), fashion has ties to conditions of self-worth; the pursuit of individuality; the relation of appearance to deeper character traits; the dynamics of social relationships, gender roles, sexuality, standards of taste, economic equality, and social class standing; and the societal effects of capitalism and mass media.

As to the peers, the respondents “got interested in what they saw or heard from their friend” with the highest weighted mean of 3.28, second is “they listen to the music or watch the same TV shows with friends” with a weighted mean of 3.13, next is the respondents “choose the same fashion style from their friends” with the weighted mean of 2.55, and last is they “suit their self just to be accepted by friends” with the lowest weighted mean of 2.53.

According to Tajfel and Turner (1979), social identity refers to the manner in which people's self-concepts are formed as a result of their membership in social groups. It also discusses exactly how collective identities influence people's attitudes and behaviours toward them in group and outgroup. When entities perceive involvement in a actual group to be underlying to their self-concept and have strong emotional connections to the group, social identity is the most dominant.

As to the Social Media, the variable “learned other foods and clothing styles through Facebook and other online platforms”, gained first with the highest weighted mean of 3.71, second is the is variable “influence the respondents is they rely more on online deliveries like Shopee, Lazada and Food Panda” with a weighted mean of 3.34, next is they “got influenced by the online advertising products” (3.05), then fourth is that they “prefer to always shop using social media such as online selling” (3.00) and placed on the last spot is the respondents are “influenced by the lifestyle of online influencers” with the lowest weighted mean of 2.74.

Social contact and the emergence of new media platforms have had a continually shifting impact on people and communication. Critical theories of race and culture have investigated these phenomena as it develops further thanks to the invention of group communication. Kellner (2003) predicted that as society continued to develop new technology and ways of communication.

Overall, the factor that influences the Criminology students the most in adapting to a foreign culture is social media, with a weighted mean of 3.17. This is in contrast to the weighted mean of 2.9 for the two factors, peers and fashion. According to Kaplan and Haenlein (2010), social media is a group of Internet-based application that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web and allow the creation and exchange of users generated content.

Table 3 Participants' Level of Enjoyment in Adapting Foreign Cultures. n=333

Level of Enjoyment	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Spend more money on expensive clothes	2.60	Neutral
Attend the concert of my favorite artist if it cost a lot	2.80	Neutral
Buying products from other merchandise	2.17	Disagree
Always get updated on all songs	2.85	Neutral
Confident in communicating with others people from different countries	2.82	Neutral
Enjoy eating street foods with my friends	3.97	Agree
Prefer imported products over local ones Even if it's more expensive	2.86	Neutral

Buy clothes regardless of the current fashion	2.91	Neutral
Buy things that are new or trendy	2.95	Neutral
Usually, care a lot about which particular brand I buy	3.03	Neutral
Would buy a brand if my favorite is endorsing it	2.97	Neutral

Legend

Scale	Range	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.51-4.50	Agree
3	2.51-3.50	Neutral
2	1.51-2.50	Disagree
1	1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree

C. Participants' Level of Enjoyment in Adapting Foreign Cultures

The table shows the level of enjoyment of the Criminology students on adapting foreign cultures.

The findings reveals that most of the respondents “*enjoy eating street foods with their friends*” with the highest weighted mean of 3.97. Additionally, the research participants indicated that they are “*neutral*” with 9 out of the 11 levels of enjoyment categories, namely; 1) *spend more money on expensive clothes* with a weighted mean of (2.60); 2) *attend the concert of my favorite artist even if it cost a lot* with a weighted mean of (2.80); 3) *always got updated on all songs* with a weighted mean of (2.85); 4) *confident in communicating with other people from different countries* with a weighted mean of (2.82); 5) *prefer imported products over local ones even if it's more expensive* with a weighted mean of (2.86); 6) *buy clothes regardless of the current fashion* with a weighted mean of (2.91); 7) *buy things that are new or trendy* with a weighted mean of (2.95); 8) *usually care a lot about which particular brand I buy* with a weighted mean of (3.03); and 9) *would buy a brand if my favorite is endorsing it* with a weighted mean of 2.97. On the other hand, others stated that they disagree on the part that includes “*buying merchandise from other pop stars*” with a weighted mean of 2.17.

The findings of this research study suggest that the reason why Korean culture has the most adapted culture among criminology students is that they are more fond when it comes to their food, clothing style, or fashion culture. In terms of their food, said students tend to eat street foods together with their friends, and as part of being students, this bonding can help them relax and ease their stress. In fashion, they are much more enlightened with Korean clothing because of the fashion and the way their artists modelled their clothing.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter displays the summary, conclusions, and recommendations established on the results of the study.

A. Summary of Findings

This study was conducted to determine the adapted foreign culture of the Criminology Students of Data Center College of the Philippines.

The participants of this study were the 333 students from all sections of the Third year and Fourth year Criminology students, who already finished Character Formation 1 and 2. It was composed of 18 students per section. The salient findings of the study are:

The foreign culture adapted by Criminology students is Korean Culture. Most of the respondents chose Korean Culture with a total of 102 out of 333 with a frequency of 30.6. The majority of the respondents are more interested in K-drama, K-pop, and Korean food as the cultures being the most adapted with a total of 102 out of 333 (30.6%). Among the three factors that influenced the respondents, social media is the factor that influenced the said respondents the most with an overall total weighted mean of 3.17.

Moreover, on the level of enjoyment in adapting to foreign culture, the majority of the respondents who chose “agree” with “eating street foods with their friends” has the highest weighted mean of 3.97. Other indicators were answered “neutral” with nine (9) out of eleven (11) responses. Moreover, the students “disagree” to “buy products from other merchandise” which has the lowest mean of 2.17.

B. Conclusions

The study yielded that majority of the Criminology students adapt the Korean foreign culture specifically, the Korean drama, K-pop, and Korean Food. As to the factors that influenced the said students in adapting to Foreign Cultures, it was determined that social media has more influence on the adaptation of foreign cultures of these students. Because of the rapid development of the products, foods, artist, influencer and others made by Korea, these students see it as positive which is why they are adapting it.

C. Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following are recommended:

- Encourage participation in patriotic activities such as *Pamulinawen* Festival. It is one of the national festivals being celebrated. Encourage the students to take part in celebrations like parades and contests regarding festivals;
- Students need language and pedagogical assistance to adapt to foreign cultures, with instruction tailored to their needs and levels of proficiency;
- The school may also strengthen the organization among international students, sponsor activities, extra and co-curricular, to encourage camaraderie and review sessions between the criminology students and foreign cultures; assign male and female faculty advisers; and possibly serve halal food;
- It is also recommended to conduct a flag ceremony every Monday, to at least maintain the student’s respect for the flag and for their own country, as well as to conduct a flag retreat every Friday;
- It is likewise important to create awareness about the rich heritage of the Philippines. Most teenagers lack of awareness about the local culture. There is a need to recommend this to give awareness to the students and teenagers, and for them to get more knowledge about
- local culture; and
- Lastly, widening the coverage of the subject Character Formation. DCCP faculty need to expand the subject. It is a good way for the students to relate to the topic themselves, and to create a learning environment that can satisfy the learning needs of more students.

D. Proposed Strategic Plan

Table 4 Strategic Plan in Strengthening the Patriotism and Nationalism of Criminology Students (Matrix)

Activity	Area of Concern	Objectives	Strategies	Time Frame	Material Needed	Responsible Person/Agency
Culture Adaptation Awareness	Criminology student's awareness	To broaden the knowledge of Criminology students when it comes in adapting a foreign culture.	Coordinate with the Criminology department of DCCP to conduct a Webinar and seek for their help regarding on the preparation and venue.	Once every Second Semester	Laptop, Internet Connection, Speakers, Zoom Account.	Students, Faculty/instructors, And Criminology department
Selling Pinoy Delicacies	Importance of Filipino Foods	To strengthen the devotion and love of every Criminology students when it comes in supporting the Filipino foods.	Coordinate with the Criminology Department to sell and promote Pinoy Delicacies inside the school premises.	Availability of time	None	Criminology students, Faculty instructors and Criminology Departments.

➤ Action plan

• Rationale

Nowadays, researchers, find out that more criminology students are fonder of foreign cultures. Social media has contribution to the factors that influenced them in adapting foreign cultures. The respondents have also been influenced by their peers and the fashion made by foreign countries. With this, the researchers created an action plan to lessen the instances of the respondents in adapting the cultures of other countries.

• Objectives

The general objective of this action plan is to strengthen the respondent in adapting foreign culture, and also to encourage them to patronize and embrace the local culture.

The specific objectives include:

- ✓ To inform them, how important it is to embrace the level of the local culture;
- ✓ To awaken them from the reality that they are adapting more the foreign culture than the local culture;
- ✓ To help them to bring back their love in their own country;
- ✓ To encourage them to choose more local products and traditions, and
- ✓ To develop those practices and to boost their patriotic behavior towards the local culture.

• Strategies

The following are the strategies that will help to attain the objective of the action plan:

The overall strategies that may use to attain the objectives of the action plan. First is the displaying of poster slogans which convey themes of patriotism and nationalism. Second, is the conduct of webinars for Criminology Students. Lastly, is to encourage them to participate in patriotic activities and programs to be implemented for the Criminology students.

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APPENDIX “A”

DATA CENTER COLLEGE OF THE PHILIPPINES
COLLEGE OF CRIMINAL JUSTICE EDUCATION
LAOAG CITY

LETTER TO THE REGISTRAR

MS. CHERRY JOY M. TADEO
School Registrar
Data Center College of The Philippines
Laoag City

Ma'am,

Greetings!

We, the Fourth-year Criminology Students of Data Center College of the Philippines Laoag City will be conducting research entitled **“FOREIGN CULTURE CONSUMPTION ON THE PATRIOTISM OF THE CRIMINOLOGY STUDENTS OF DATA CENTER COLLEGE OF THE PHILIPPINES, LAOAG CITY”**. In order to achieve the goal of our research, we are asking your permission to have the total number of third-year and fourth-year criminology students who are currently enrolled in the school year 2022–2023. In order to achieve the goal of our research.

Rest assured that all the information provided will be kept confidential and would be utilized for research purposes only.

Thank you for your consideration and we are looking forward that our request would merit your positive response.

Respectfully Yours,

John Angelo Alos
ALOS, JOHN ANGELO
Leslie Ann F. Carba
CARBA, LESLIE ANN F.
John Gillo Ronchezka
GILO, RONCHEZKA
Rica Jea Ofilas
OFILAS, RICA JEA
Jovie Ann Santos
SANTOS, JOVIE ANN

Rovilyn Amor R. Balolong
BALOLONG, ROVILYN AMOR R.
Hans Christian Ferrer
FERRER, HANS CHRISTIAN
Mayck Jhoenell Lomboy
LOMBOY, MAYCK JHOENELL
Bryan Ramos
RAMOS, BRYAN
Marlon T. Tagalicud
TAGALICUD, MARLON T.

Noted by:

Jay-Lynne May S. Escalona
MS. JAY-LYNNE MAY S. ESCALONA, MSCrim
Research Adviser

“APPENDIX B”

DATA CENTER COLLEGE OF THE PHILIPPINES
COLLEGE OF CRIMINAL JUSTICE EDUCATION
LAOAG CITY

LETTER TO CONDUCT THE STUDY

DR. MATHEW P. LANGBIS
Dean, College of Criminal Justice Education
Data Center College of The Philippines
Laoag City

Sir,

Greetings with love and peace!

The undersigned Fourth-year criminology students currently enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Criminology at Data Center College of the Philippines, Laoag City is presently conducting a research study entitled “**FOREIGN CULTURE CONSUMPTION ON THE PATRIOTISM OF THE CRIMINOLOGY STUDENTS OF DATA CENTER COLLEGE OF THE PHILIPPINES, LAOAG CITY**”. The purpose of conducting this study is to determine the foreign cultures that the DCCP Criminology students usually patronize, their level of enjoyment, and the factors that influence them in patronizing foreign cultures.

For this matter, the researchers are asking for your favorable approval to conduct the study. This would be a great help in completing this research.

Rest assured that all the data gathered from our respondents will be kept at the highest level of confidentiality and would be utilized for research purposes only. Thank you for your consideration and we are looking forward that our request would merit your positive response.

Respectfully Yours,

[Signature]
ALOS, JOHN ANGELO

[Signature]
CARBA, LESLIE ANN F.

[Signature]
GILO, RONCHEZKA

[Signature]
OFILAS, RISA JEA

[Signature]
SANTOS, JOVIE ANN

[Signature]
BALOLONG, ROVILYN AMOR R.

[Signature]
FERRER, HANS CHRISTIAN

[Signature]
LOMBOY, MAYER JHOENELL

[Signature]
RAMOS, BRYAN

[Signature]
TAGALICUD, MARLON T.

Noted by:

[Signature]
MRS. JAYEYNE MAY S. ESCALONA, MSCrim
Research Adviser

Approved by:

[Signature]
DR. MATHEW P. LANGBIS
Dean, College of Criminal Justice Education, DCCP

“APPENDIX C”

**DATA CENTER COLLEGE OF THE PHILIPPINES
COLLEGE OF CRIMINAL JUSTICE EDUCATION
LAOAG CITY**

LETTER TO THE RESPONDENTS

Dear Respondents,

The undersigned Fourth-year criminology students currently enrolled in Bachelor of Science in Criminology at Data Center College of the Philippines, Laoag City is presently conducting a research study entitled “FOREIGN CULTURE CONSUMPTION ON THE PATRIOTISM OF THE CRIMINOLOGY STUDENTS OF DATA CENTER COLLEGE OF THE PHILIPPINES, LAOAG CITY”. The purpose of conducting this study is to determine the foreign cultures that the DCCP Criminology students usually patronize, their level of enjoyment, and the factors that influence them in patronizing foreign cultures.

For this matter, the researchers are asking for your favorable approval to conduct the study. This would be a great help in completing this research.

Rest assured that all the data gathered from our respondents will be kept at the highest level of confidentiality and would be utilized for research purposes only.

Your positive response to this request will be a valuable contribution to our study's success and will be highly appreciated. Thank you very much for your cooperation.

Respectfully Yours,

ALOS, JOHN ANGELO

CARBA, LESLIE ANN F.

GILO, RONCHEZKA

OFILAS, RICA JEA

SANTOS, JOVIE ANN

BALOLONG, ROVILYN AMOR R.

FERRER, HANS CHRISTIAN

LOMBOY, MAYCK JHOENELL

RAMOS, BRYAN

TAGALCUD, MARLON T.

Noted by:
MS. JAY-LYNNE MAY S. ESCALONA, MSCrim
 Research Adviser

APPENDIX “D”

DATA CENTER COLLEGE OF THE PHILIPPINES
COLLEGE OF CRIMINAL JUSTICE EDUCATION
LAOAG CITY

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

“Foreign Culture Consumption on The Patriotism of The Criminology Students of Data Center College of The Philippines, Laoag City”.

Respondents No: _____

Direction: Please answer all the following questions based on your own perception. Choose one and place a checkmark (✓) in the appropriate box to indicate your answer.

Part 1. Foreign culture that I patronized as a criminology student.

FOREIGN CULTURES:

- | | | |
|---|--|--|
| ☐ Korean Cultures | ☐ American Cultures | ☐ Indian Cultures |
| ☐ Chinese Cultures | ☐ European Cultures | ☐ others; _____ |
| ☐ Vietnam Cultures | ☐ Japanese Cultures | |

Please state and specify: _____

Direction: Please put a checkmark (✓) and rate yourself honestly based on what you actually do. Give the statements using the following scales:

Scale Descriptive Interpretation

- 5 - Strongly Agree
- 4 - Agree
- 3 - Neither agree
- 2 - Disagree
- 1 - Strongly disagree

Part 5 Factors Influencing Participants’ Patriotism to Foreign Cultures.

FACTORS	Rating				
	5	4	3	2	1
Fashion					
I buy new fashionable clothes only when they are well-accepted.					
I got interested in buying items used by celebrities.					
I copy the hairstyles of celebrities.					
I purchase clothes based on quality and design.					
I prefer to buy branded clothes rather than local ones.					
I buy clothes endorsed by my favorite celebrities.					
It is risky to buy unbranded products because of their low quality.					
Peers					
I got interested in what I saw or heard from my friends.					
I choose the same fashion style as my friends.					
I listen to the same music or watch the same TV show with my friends.					
I suit myself just to be accepted by my friends.					
Social Media					
I learned other food and clothing styles through Facebook and other online platforms.					
I rely more on online deliveries like shoppee, Lazada, food panda, etc.					
I got influenced by the online advertising products					
I got influenced by the lifestyle of online influencers.					
I prefer to always shop using social media such as online selling.					

Part 6 Participants’ Level of Enjoyment in Patronizing Foreign Cultures.

LEVEL OF ENJOYMENT	5	4	3	2	1
I spend more money on expensive clothes.					
I attend the concert of my favorite artist’ even if it cost a lot.					
I buy merchandise from other pop stars.					
I always got updated on all songs.					
I am confident in communicating with other people from different countries.					
I enjoy eating street foods with my friends.					
I prefer imported products over local ones even if it is more expensive.					
I buy clothes regardless of the current fashion.					
I buy things that are new or trendy.					
I usually care a lot about which particular brand I buy.					
I would buy a brand if my favorite is endorsing it.					

Thank you very much for your cooperation!

APPENDIX “E”

Documentation on the distribution of the questionnaires to third-year and fourth-year Criminology students at Data Center College of the Philippines, Brgy. 1 San Lorenzo, Laoag City Ilocos Norte.

Description: The researcher conducted a survey questionnaire among the criminology students who finished the subject Character Formation 1 and 2 and explained to them the said questionnaire entitled “Adaptation of Criminology Students to Foreign Cultures.” How their response is important to the success of the study.